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A Creative Folio

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Sangkay

Kaupod, kaugop ha kalibutan
Madali daupan kon mayda pannginahanglan
Dire masige ikaw papabay-an
Kay hinigugma kon tiupay, ikaw sangkay!

Waray mabalyo, han imo kaupay
Bisan hirayo, dayon ka nangangampay
Ha kakurian ngan kalipay
Dire gud mawawara iton tinuod nga sangkay.

Makuri man imo kinabuhi,
Ha imo ngirit, imo gin papaagi,
Istorya, buwa, ngan kaagi
Dire nawawara kon adi kala pirme.

Siring pa nimo paghulat,
Kay an grasya malaksi dumangat
Akon kalipay, kalipay mo liwat
Tungod hito, damo nga salamat!